

Borehole-Integrated Electric Drilling Robot for Shallow Geothermal Energy

Bohrlochintegrierter, elektrischer Bohrroboter für die oberflächennahe Geothermie

Dr. Hans-Jörg Dennig

Zurich University of Applied Sciences / Borobotics AG

Keywords: Shallow Geothermal Energy, Autonomous Drilling Robot, Electric Borehole Drilling

Abstract

Conventional drilling technologies for geothermal probes face technical, ecological, and economic limits in urban areas. Large diesel-powered rigs require extensive space, create high noise emissions, and depend on scarce skilled labour and machine availability—factors that slow down the energy transition.

The novel *Grabowski* drilling robot developed by Borobotics operates fully electrically and autonomously within the borehole—without drill pipes or a surface rig. It integrates a rotary-percussive drive, a hydraulic movement system, a closed-loop water flushing circuit, and an extrusion unit that stabilises the borehole wall. This compact technology enables boreholes of up to 500 m depth even in confined environments such as parking decks or courtyards.

Laboratory and initial field tests verified drilling speeds up to 1 cm per minute with approximately 10 kWh of electrical energy per 200 m borehole—equating to an 86 % CO₂ reduction compared to conventional methods. The quiet operation, low footprint, and autonomous control open new applications for shallow geothermal energy and significantly reduce labour and installation costs.

This paper presents the system concept, current development results, and a scalable business model for drilling companies, illustrating how autonomous electric drilling can accelerate the decarbonisation of building heating.

1. Introduction and Motivation

Heating buildings with shallow geothermal energy (SGE) is one of the most efficient and sustainable ways to achieve climate-neutral heat generation. Ground-source heat pumps (GSHP) can reduce CO₂ emissions enormously compared with fossil heating (Bauer et al., 2018; Breisig, 2021; Sabel and Schreinermacher, 2021; Thomas et al., 2022; “Übersicht – Geothermie Schweiz,” n.d.).

However, the drilling process for geothermal probes has remained largely unchanged for decades. Diesel compressors, heavy rigs, and large drilling sites (> 50 m²) make conventional drilling costly and often impossible in dense urban areas. Noise emissions exceed 120 dBA, and a single 200 m borehole requires about 740 L of diesel (≈ 2 t CO₂). Moreover, long waiting times of 9–18 months arise from machine shortages and lack of skilled workers.

Borobotics AG, a spin-off from the Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW), addresses these challenges with a fully electric, borehole-integrated drilling robot that works autonomously without a surface rig Fig 1.

Fig 1: Comparison of conventional vs. borehole-integrated drilling setup

2. System Concept of the Grabowski Robot

The *Grabowski* system integrates all drilling functions directly into the borehole. Instead of a 6 m tower and a 20-tonne rig, the robot itself - about 2.7 m long and \varnothing 136 mm - contains the full drilling mechanism and communicates with a compact surface unit comprising only a pump, filter, and water tank (\approx 8 m² footprint; see Fig 2).

Fig 2: Visualisation of the future system in the smallest of spaces (left); Size comparison: Klemm KR 708-3GW, person, *Grabowski* (right)

2.1 Main modules

Each module is designed as a self-contained functional unit, enabling rapid maintenance and modular upgrades (Fig 3). The mechanical and electronic interfaces follow a standardized architecture, allowing the system to be scaled from 130 mm to 250 mm bore diameters. Combined, these modules form a fully autonomous drilling platform capable of adapting to varying geological conditions with minimal human intervention:

Fig 3: System overview of the *Grabowski*; *Grabowski* Prototype 2.X (right)

1. Electric drill and gearbox

A 7 kW rotary-percussive drive operates an innovative overburden bit that can cut in both hard and loose rock. Integrated vibration sensors adapt the hammering and rotation frequency in real time.

2. Water-based flushing system

A closed water cycle removes the cuttings from the borehole while continuously re-filtering and re-using the water. Only 3.5 m³ of container volume are required for a 200 m borehole.

3. Movement unit

Two inflatable packers (fluid muscles) and a hydraulic cylinder alternately anchor and extend the robot, transmitting torque and forward motion without external force.

4. Extrusion and support unit

A Polyethylene (PE) pipe is extruded along the borehole wall to stabilise loose formations

and seal water layers. This allows drilling in soft sediments and even in groundwater protection zones.

5. Safety and monitoring

Integrated pressure sensors and a remote monitoring interface enable autonomous operation. A mechanical preventer and winch system can close the borehole or retract the robot in case of emergency.

2.2 Operating principle

The robot drills, moves, and stabilises the borehole sequentially while submerged in water. The closed hydraulic system ensures low noise and low energy consumption. At completion, the robot retracts autonomously or via safety cable, after which a standard double-U pipe probe is inserted and backfilled (Fig 4).

Fig 4: Process of borehole creation and probe integration

3 Development Progress (2023–2025)

Since 2023 the technology has advanced from TRL 4 to TRL 6. The ongoing project is funded by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (BFE, SI/502692) and by Innosuisse SIP (109.464 SIP-EE).

Laboratory phase (2023–2024):

- Verified drilling speeds: 1 cm/min (granite), 1.7 cm/min (sandstone), 5 cm/min (clay).
- Energy consumption: \approx 10 kWh electric energy
- Stable extrusion of \varnothing 136 mm PE pipes (wet + dry tests).
- Movement and sealing systems tested up to 20 m head pressure.

Field phase (2024–2025, Winterthur Test Site; see Fig 5):

- 20 m borehole drilled autonomously in solid rock.
- Continuous operation > 150 h (“equivalent 50 m borehole”).
- Fully integrated filtration system proven at 20 m depth.
- GUI / control software established between robot and operator.

Fig 5: Field test at Stadtwerk Winterthur (20 m depth, September 2025): Drill rig and cable management (left), Filter and debris unit (right)

4 Results and Performance

The main results demonstrate the feasibility of autonomous, electric drilling for geothermal applications.

Parameter	Conventional system	Grabowski Prototype	Reduction
CO ₂ emissions	2 000 kg	288 kg	– 86 %
Noise level	120 dBA	< 60 dBA	– 94 %
Site area	> 50 m ²	\approx 8 m ²	– 84 %
Operators	2–3	0 (on-site)	– 100 %

Drilling precision is estimated to ± 1 % vertical deviation per 100 m. The slow drilling speed enables early detection of water layers and controlled response. The total process time for a 200 m borehole is ≈ 13 days autonomous operation, which is competitive when considering minimal personnel involvement and simultaneous multi-robot operation.

5 Applications and Demonstration Sites

The compact and quiet operation opens entirely new use cases for geothermal drilling:

- Urban retrofits: Drilling in small courtyards or narrow alleys without disturbing neighbours.
- Underground parking decks: Potential for vertical geothermal probes under buildings (Fig 6).
- Sensitive zones: Possible operation in groundwater protection areas due to closed-loop water system.
- Industrial and infrastructure projects: Horizontal or inclined drilling for energy networks and waste-heat recovery.

Two demonstration projects are planned:

- Q2/26: 50 m drilling including extrusion and probe installation.
- Q4/26: 200 m integrated system test (TRL 7).

Fig 6: Potential application scenario: drilling inside a parking garage

6 Market and Business Perspective

Borobotics applies a B2B “drilling-by-the-meter” model. Drilling companies rent the robots via a one-time setup fee and pay a variable fee of ca. 15-20 € per meter drilled. Borobotics retains ownership and provides remote control, maintenance, and software (Fig 7).

This model transforms drilling from a high-CAPEX to a service-based, scalable business. One team of two persons can operate ≈ 13 robots in parallel, tripling annual revenue and margins.

The market entry is planned for 2027 (Switzerland) and 2028 (Germany), with pilot projects already secured through Letters of Intent from major drilling firms in Switzerland and Germany.

Fig 7: Business model: “Drilling by the meter” concept

7 Environmental and Economic Impact

By replacing diesel compressors with electric autonomous systems, *Grabowski* reduces the carbon footprint of geothermal boreholes dramatically.

For each 200 m borehole:

- CO₂ savings ≈ 1.7 t
- Energy savings ≈ 19 000 kWh

If 730 000 boreholes are drilled between 2026 and 2034 in Switzerland and Germany, the potential CO₂ reduction exceeds 1.25 million tons. Moreover, the compact setup and automation reduce urban disruption, eliminate heavy transport, and enable new construction approaches (e.g., retrofit geothermal fields under existing buildings).

From an economic perspective, autonomous drilling triples profitability for drilling companies and makes geothermal systems ≈ 30 % cheaper for end customers.

8 Outlook

The next development steps focus on system integration and autonomy:

- Q2/2026 – 50 m Integrated Test: All modules (gearbox, movement, extrusion, filtration) in continuous operation.
- Q4/2026 – 200 m Full Demonstration: Showcase borehole and heat pump installation.
- Q4/2027 – Market Launch: Start of commercial deployment and certification process.
- Q4/2028+ – Expansion: Germany, Nordics and international partnerships.

Parallel to technical advances, Borobotics is building a network of manufacturing partners and supply chains for series production (Technopark Winterthur and ZHAW infrastructure).

Long-term applications include horizontal drilling for energy networks, foundation cooling, and subsurface heat storage.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (BFE) under Project SI/502692 and the Swiss Innovation Agency Innosuisse (Project 109.464 SIP-EE – *Autonomous Drilling Robot for Shallow Geothermal Energy*).

Sources

Bauer, M., Freeden, W., Jacobi, H., Neu, T. (Eds.), 2018. Handbuch Oberflächennahe Geothermie. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-50307-2>

Breisig, D.V., 2021. Der Wechsel zur Wärmepumpe als Treiber neuer Geschäftsmodelle.

Sabel, M., Schreinermacher, J., 2021. Roadmap Wärmepumpe - Der Weg zur Dekarbonisierung des Gebäudesektors. Bundesverband Wärmepumpe (BWP) e. V., Berlin.

Thomas, S., Schwürer, D., Vondung, F., Wagner, O., 2022. Heizen ohne Öl und Gas bis 2035 – ein Sofortprogramm für erneuerbare Wärme und effiziente Gebäude. Im Auftrag von Greenpeace e.V.

Übersicht – Geothermie Schweiz [WWW Document], n.d. URL <https://geothermie-schweiz.ch/geothermie/geothermie-uebersicht/> (accessed 6.22.22).

Hans-Jörg Dennig
Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Lagerplatz 22, 8400 Winterthur, Switzerland
Borobotics AG, , Technoparkstr. 2, 8406 Winterthur, Switzerland
hans-joerg.dennig@zhaw.ch, hans-joerg.dennig@borobotics.ch